

UTOPIA OF GLOBAL EDUCATION

A Peer Reviewed Refereed International Research Journal

ONLINE ISSN-2454-7387

Volume II, Issue I, June 2016, pp. 10-16

www.srsshodhsansthan.org

A Study of Uses of Social Networking Sites among Adolescent Girls of Senior Secondary School of Agra District

Dr. Dolly Rani¹ & Anita Verma²

**¹ Lecturer, ² Research Scholar, Department of Extension, Communication and Management
Institute of Home Science**

Dr. B.R. Ambedkar University, Agra, India

Abstract

During the last two decades the world, in general and India, in particular has witnessed for remarkable changes in information technology (IT). The advancement in IT led to the emergence of Social Networking Sites (SNS). Adolescent boys and girls are more interested in using advanced technology in every field compare to any other age group It is also true in the case of medium of communication. The EDUCATION data showed that the percentage of adolescents who said they never use SNS has fallen from 25% to 11% in 2008. Today in India particularly among the adolescent boys and girls, the usage of Social Networking Sites (SNS) has significantly increased and it certainly has for reaching impacts on the academic and other activities of the adolescents. Hence, this study entitled "A Study of Uses of Social Networking Sites among Adolescents Girls of Senior Secondary School of Agra District" is placed in this context, aimed at presenting the pattern of uses of SNS by the adolescent girls of senior secondary school of Agra district. A multistage random sampling was used for the selection of sample. Total fifty respondents were taken as a sample. Survey method was used for collecting the data. Data was collected with the help of questionnaire specially drafted for the purpose.

A careful observation of the data regarding to the uses of internet shows that all the respondents (100 percent) were used the internet. The data regarding to the use of Social Networking Sites shows that out of the 50 respondents only 38 (76 percent) respondents used Social Networking Sites. The data further shows that out of the 38 respondents who were using Social Networking Sites all the respondents (100 percent) were used Face book, Whatsapp, Google + and Orkut.

Keywords: Social Networking Sites.

Introduction

During the last two decades the world, in general and India, in particular has witnessed for remarkable changes in information technology (IT). The advancement in IT led to the emergence of Social Networking Sites (SNS). SNS are currently being used regular by millions of people. The usage of SNS has been so widespread that they have caught the attention of

academic worldwide. Social Networking Sites have rapidly gained popularity. Globally the active membership on SNS reached 300 million on 2010.

Social Networking Site can be broadly defined as internet –based social spaces designed to facilities communication, collaboration and content sharing across networks of contacts. Social Networking Sites allow users to manage build and represent their social networks online. Social Networking Sites are usually made up of other individuals: they might also include profiles of events, companies, even political parties. People use social networking sites for countless activities. Among the most common uses are connecting with existing networks, making and developing friendship/contacts, create an online presence for their users, viewing contacts/finding information, creating and customizing profile and so on.

A social network is a collection of individuals linked together by a set of relations. A social networking service consists of a representation of each user (often a profile), his or her social links, and a variety of additional services. Social Networking Sites are web –based services connections and views and cross the connection within the system.

According to Boyd and Ellison “Social Networking Sites are web based services that allowed to individuals to:

- Construct a public and semi public profile within a bounded system.
- Articulate a list of other users with whom they share a connection.
- View and traverse their list of connections and those made by others within the

system. The nature and nomenclature of these connections may vary from site to site.

The usage of SNS has been so widespread that they have caught the attention of academic worldwide. The usage of Social Networking Sites (SNS) among the people of India is evidently increasing, particularly among the adolescent boys and girls.

A research study conducted by **Dutton W.H. (2004)** reported that in Social Networking Sites, sharing of private information and giving updates of day to day happening is a latest trend. These sites heavily cater to the young brigade especially the age group between 15 to 25 years.

It has invariable left a big impact on social in general and adolescent boys and girls in particular. Today in India particularly among the adolescent boys and girls, the usage of Social Networking Sites (SNS) has significantly increased and it certainly has for reaching impacts on the academic and other activities of the adolescents. These impacts are so widespread that they caught the attention of Social scientists worldwide.

G. Sawati and D. Debarati (2014) reported in their study that Social Networking Sites allowing the young users the opportunity to mingle with a huge network of known as well as unknown friends. It has become like an addiction for the young adults to create online profiles and certainly they were hooked to mobile phones, laptops and PCs. Accessing the internet through the mobile phones has made it even easier for the young generations to get logged –in into facebook, Orkut or Twitter most of the time and post updates about their daily activities. Participating in the Social Networking Sites and having an increased number of friends on the list is supposed to be a trend that cannot be ignored in any way.

However, the range of studies conducted to deal with the usage of SNS among adolescent girls in negligible in India. Hence, this study entitled “**A Study of Uses of Social Networking Sites among Adolescents Girls of Senior Secondary School of Agra District**” is placed in this context, aimed at presenting usage pattern of SNS by the adolescent girls of senior secondary school of Agra district.

Methodology

Research design used for the present study was exploratory research design. A multistage random sampling was used for the selection of sample. Twenty five adolescent girls from one Hindi medium college namely “Bharat memorial inter college” and one English medium college namely “M.S. public school” were randomly selected for the study. Thus total fifty respondents were taken as a sample.

Survey method was used for collecting the data. Data was collected with the help of questionnaire specially drafted for the purpose.

For the present study primary and secondary data was collected. Primary data was collected with the help of self made questionnaire which was specially designed for this purpose. Secondary data was collected from both published and unpublished sources from various institutions, agencies, libraries and internet etc.

Based on the nature of data and information class interval and percentage were used for statistical analysis in the study.

Result & Discussion

Analysis is an important aspect of the research analysis makes the data more meaningful the study more significant. The data regarding to the uses of internet/social networking sites presented under the following heads:

- Use of internet
- Use of social networking sites
- Pattern of uses of different social networking sites

Uses of Internet

Table 1. Uses of internet

Question	Responses	Number	Percentage
Do you use internet	Yes	50	100.00
	No	0	0.00
	Total	50	100.00
Where do you use internet generally**	Your home	44	88.00
	Your school	6	12.00
	Internet club	6	12.00
	Your friends Home	12	24.00
Frequency do use of internet	Daily	18	36.00
	Weekly	20	40.00
	Monthly	4	8.00
	Occasionally	8	16.00
	Total	50	100.00

** Multiple responses [percentage are calculated on the basis total of number of respondents (N=50)]

A careful observation of table no.1 shows that all the respondents (100 percent) were used the internet.

When the question was asked with the respondents about the place where they used internet, majority of the respondents 88 percent said that they used internet at their home, while only 12 percent respondents said that they used the internet at their school and internet club. The data further shows that remaining 24 percent respondents used the internet at their friend's home.

As regarding to the frequency of use of internet the result reveals that majority of the respondents (40 percent) used the internet weekly and 36 percent respondents used the internet daily. Only 16 percent and 8 percent respondents used the internet occasionally and monthly respectively.

Uses of Social Networking Sites

Table 2. Uses of Social Networking Sites

<i>Responses</i>	<i>Number</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
<i>Yes</i>	38	76.00
<i>No</i>	12	24.00
<i>Total</i>	<i>50</i>	<i>100.00</i>

Table 2. depicts the data regarding to the use of Social Networking Sites. The findings show that out of the 50 respondents only 38 (76 percent) respondents used Social networking Sites.

Pattern of Uses of Different Social Networking Sites

Table.3. Pattern of uses of different Social Networking Sites

Social Networking Sites	Visiting of various Social networking sites (N=38)				Frequency of visiting of various Social networking sites								N
	Yes		No		Daily		Weekly		Monthly		Some Time		
	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	NO	%	
Facebook	38	100.00	00	00	8	21.05	16	42.11	8	21.05	6	15.79	38
My Space	8	21.05	30	78.95	4	50.00	2	25.00	2	25.00	–	–	8
Twitter	12	31.58	26	68.42	4	33.33	4	33.33	2	16.67	2	16.67	12
Whatsapp	38	100.00	00	00	12	31.57	16	42.11	6	15.79	4	10.53	38
My opera	12	31.58	26	68.42	4	33.33	4	33.33	2	16.67	2	16.67	12
Millat facebook	2	5.26	36	94.74	–	–	–	–	–	–	2	100.00	2
Google+	38	100.00	00	00	16	42.11	12	31.58	6	15.78	4	10.53	38
Any Other (Orkut)	38	100.00	00	00	14	36.84	10	26.05	8	21.05	6	15.79	38

The data regarding to the use of various Social Networking Sites presented in Table 3. to be quite interesting. The finding show that out of the 38 respondents who were using Social Networking Sites all the respondents (100 percent) were used Face book, Whatsapp, Google +

and Orkut. The data further shows that out of the 38 respondents 31.58 percent of the respondents were using Twitter and My opera while 21.05 percent of the respondents were using My Space and only 5.26 percent of the respondents were using Millat Face book.

Regarding to the frequency of use of Social Networking Sites the data shows that out of the 38 respondents who were using Face book 21.05 percent respondents were using Face book daily while 42.11 percent of the respondents using Face book weekly. Only 21.05 percent and 15.79 percent the respondents were using Face book monthly and some time respectfully.

Regarding to the frequency of use of My Space the data shows that out of the 8 respondents who were using my Space 50 percent of the respondents were using my Space daily and 25 percent of the respondents were using my Space weekly. Remaining 25 percent of the respondents were using my Space monthly.

In reference to the Twitter the data shows that out of the 12 respondents who were using Twitter, 33.33 percent of the respondents were using Twitter daily as same as weekly The data further shows that number of respondents who were using Twitter monthly and Some time were Same as 16.67 percent.

In regard to the Whatsapp the result shows that out of the 38 respondents who were using Whatsapp, 31.57 percent of the respondents were using Whatsapp daily, while 42.11 percents of the respondents were using Whatsapp weekly. The data further shows that 15.79 percent of the respondents were using Whatsapp monthly and only 10.53 percent of the respondents were using Whatsapp some time

In reference to the frequency of use of the Millat Face book. Out of the 2 respondents who were using Millat Face book, 100 percent of the respondents were using Millat Face book some time.

In reference to the My Opera the data shows that out of the 12 respondents who were using My Opera, 33.33 percent of the respondents were using My Opera daily as same as weekly. The data further shows that number of respondents who were using My Opera monthly and some time were same as 16.67 percent.

In regard to the Google+ the result shows that out of the 38 respondents who were using Google+, 42.11 percent of the respondents were using Google+ daily , while 31.58 percent of the respondents were using Google+ weekly. The data further shows that 15.78 percent of the

respondents were using Google+ monthly and only 10.53 percent of the respondents were using Google+ some time.

In reference to the frequency of use of Orkut the data shows that out of the 38 respondents who were using Orkut 36.84 percent respondents using Orkut daily while 26.05 percent of the respondents were using Orkut weekly .The data Further shows that 21.05 percent of the respondents were using Orkut monthly and only 15.79 percent the respondents were using Orkut some time.

Conclusion

A careful observation of the data regarding to the uses of internet shows that all the respondents (100 percent) were used the internet. As regarding to the frequency of use of internet the result reveals that majority of the respondents (40 percent) used the internet weekly and 36 percent respondents used the internet daily. Only 16 percent and 8 percent respondents used the internet occasionally and monthly respectively.

The data regarding to the use of Social Networking Sites shows that out of the 50 respondents only 38 (76 percent) respondents used Social networking Sites. The data regarding to the use of various Social Networking Sites was to be quite interesting. The finding show that out of the 38 respondents who were using Social Networking Sites all the respondents (100 percent) were used Facebook, Whatsapp, Google + and Orkut.

Reference

- **Dutton, W.H. (2004)**, “Social transformation in an information society: rethinking access to you and the world”. UNESCO Archives English- UNESCO HQ Sciences SSDCN (stock2E) -UNESCO Brasilia.
- <http://www.unesco.or/new/en/communication-and-transformation-in-aninformation-society-rethinking-access-to-you-and-the-world>.
- **Saswati Gangopadhyay & Debarati Dhar (2014)**, "Social Networking Sites and Privacy Issues Concerning Youths" Global Media Journal Indian Edition, University of Calcutta, Vol. 5(1), ISSN 2249-5835.